

A Study on Critical Equipment Element Maintenance Services Requirements in Distillery Industry

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ABSTRACT

India is among the fastest growing alcohol markets in the world, witnesses a high rate of increase in population in urban areas. The spending power of the middle-class population is improving with the economy, which is contributing to the high consumption of alcohol in India. The analysis of the alcohol market size is based on different types of products, consumption among different states, retail channel and imported and domestic. The Indian alcohol industry is found to be segmented into IMFL (Indian made foreign liquor), Wine, Beer, IMIL (Indian made Indian liquor) and imported alcohol with latter's share of 0.8% in the Indian market. The increasing demand for alcohol and spirits has resulted in the development of the distillery industry and its services. This research highlights the types of critical equipment, service requirement and the gap between the services provided by suppliers to distilleries. The purpose of the study is to study critical equipment, its maintenance requirements of critical equipment and the critical service components of distillery affecting service quality gaps in the distillery industry. The research is based on secondary data. A model is developed to manage the safety critical equipment, devices and systems.

KEYWORDS: Critical equipment, Services gap, Services requirement, Critical equipment, Element maintenance, Distillery industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of alcohol as a drink is an age-old story in India and it appears that the technique for fermentation and distillation was available even in the Vedic times. It was then called "Somarasa" and was used not only for its invigorating effect, but also in worship and medicinal uses. To date, not only has the consumption of alcohol being continued, but it is an integral part of the Ayurvedic system of medicine. The First distillery in the country was set up at Cawnpore (Kanpur) in 1805 by Carew & Co. Ltd., for the manufacture of Rum for the army. The technique of fermentation, distillation and blending of alcoholic beverages was developed in our country on the lines of practices adopted overseas particularly in Europe. However, the rapid advancement in technology and through various innovations in the art of fermentation has progressed by leaps and bounds and recoveries have improved tremendously.

The distillery industry today consists broadly of two parts, one potable liquor and the industrial alcohol, including anhydrous ethanol for blending with petrol. The potable industry producing Indian Made Foreign Liquor and Country Liquor has a steady but limited demand with a growth rate of about 7-10 percent per annum. The industrial alcohol industry, on the other hand, is showing a declining trend because of the high price of Molasses which is invariably used as a substrate for the production of alcohol. The alcohol produced is now being utilised in the ratio of approximately 52 percent for portable and the balance 48 percent for industrial and ethanol for blending with petrol, use. Over the years the potable liquor industry has shown remarkable results in

the production of high-quality spirits. The Indian Liquor industry is today exporting a sizable quantity of Indian Liquor products to other countries.

The utilisation of Ethyl alcohol or Ethanol, now popularly known as alcohol, for industrial use is a recent phenomenon and its importance came into being towards the end of the second world war. With protection being granted to the sugar Industry in 1932, a large number of sugar factories were established in the country, particularly in Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh where irrigation facilities existed for the cultivation of sugarcane. This increase resulted in the accumulation of molasses, which resultantly, caused unmanageable environmental problems. At that time the demand for molasses was almost insignificant and the sugar mills had to incur some expenditure on the removal of this bye product i.e. molasses. For resolving these problems, a joint committee of U.P. and Bihar was constituted to explore the possibilities of developing alcohol based industries for the purpose of utilisation of molasses. The Committee in its report recommended the establishment of distilleries for production of alcohol, utilising molasses as substrate. It also recommended that alcohol produced by the distilleries should be admixed with petrol, to supplement motor fuel. The production of alcohol did not only help in solving the problems of disposal of molasses, but it also filled up the gap in the demand and supply of motor spirit. As a substantial quantity of alcohol after meeting its requirement for the manufacture of gasohol alcohol was diverted for production of alcohol-based chemicals in different parts of the country. The utilisation of alcohol for this purpose progressed steadily and a substantial quantity of alcohol produced in the country is now being utilised for the manufacture of solvents and intermediates. Till a few years back a little more than 50% alcohol produced in the country was being utilised for production of alcohol-based chemicals, but after the decontrol of molasses in the year 1993, the utilisation of alcohol for production of chemicals, dyestuff, synthetic rubber, polymers and plastics, etc. has received a setback.

However, with the advent of ethanol blending with petrol/ motor fuel, the requirement of ethanol/ industrial alcohol has increased manifold in the country to the extent that in case 5-10 % blending, if made mandatory all over the country, the sugar factory molasses available in the country shall not prove to be adequate for meeting the total requirement of ethanol including its use for potable liquors and other industrial uses. The alcohol industry has a total installed capacity of 4200 million liters of alcohol in a year. However, the licensed capacity is concentrated in three states of U.P., Maharashtra and Tamilnadu. With the announcement of the Government of India to make the blending of motor fuel with ethanol up to 5 % mandatory and to raise it to 10% by the year 2017-18, a substantial increase in the requirement, as well as production capacity of ethanol, is expected and a large number of ethanol distilleries are on the anvil of installation. The ethanol is being mixed with petrol up to 20% to 25 % in Brazil and nearly 30 -40 % in the USA particularly in the state of California. India, therefore, has to immediately look for other sources of feedstock for the production of ethanol for increasing the total production and meeting the requirement of ethanol even for 5-10% blending with petrol, coupled with further increasing the availability of molasses through an increase in sugar cane production and sugar mill's capacity. Thus the distillery industry is destined to play a very important and vital role in the nation's economic and industrial scenario in the near future.

2. OBJECTIVES

- To find out the critical equipment in the distillery industry
- To study the maintenance requirements of critical equipment in the distillery industry
- To find out the critical service components of distillery affecting service quality gaps in the distillery industry

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Industrial Alcohol Distillation Process and Equipment at BM Engineering we pride ourselves on the professional service and high-quality equipment that we supply to the distilling industry. Distilling is one of our biggest sectors, providing only the best brands for distilleries throughout Scotland and the rest of the world. Our product range has continually increased due to the ever-rising demand for distilling valves, instrumentation and associated equipment within this sector. We have the exact distilling valves to meet your unique requirements. Before any equipment can be purchased and installed, we must first understand the industrial alcohol distillation process. Below you will find information on the industrial alcohol distillation process and equipment. What is the alcohol distillation process? The distillation process is the method of separating the substances from a liquid mixture by boiling and condensing. The distillation of fermented products is what produces distilled beverages with high alcohol content. At BM Engineering, we supply a variety of whiskey distilleries

in Scotland including Glen Moray Distillery. Therefore, we have an in-depth understanding of what is required. There are several steps to the basic industrial alcohol distillation process. These include 1- Begin with some kind of fermented alcohol, usually wine or beer. Or more accurately, wash. Wash is the finished product of fermentation that is ready for distillation for the first time. 2- Heat the wash. The alcohol in the wash will turn to steam before the water does, this is due to the fact that alcohol boils at a lower temperature than water. The alcohol will then rise up in the still. 3- Collect the alcohol vapors. 4- Chill the vapors so they condense back into a liquid. 5- Collect the alcohol from the still. Industrial alcohol distillation equipment in BM Engineering, we supply a range of distilling equipment to help support your industrial distillery processes. Our extensive knowledge and years of experience working with the distilling industry, ensure we are able to supply the correct product for each stage of the process.

4. DEFINING CRITICAL EQUIPMENT

In the realm of facility management, there are assets that are absolutely mission critical to the business, especially as they pertain to building operations. The failure of these critical assets is the very risk that must be mitigated if not eliminated. As with all business practices, managing critical equipment requires an auditable process to ensure that the operational risk reduction is actively pursued in addition to all other pertinent business objectives. Critical equipment refers to vessels, machinery, piping, alarms, interlocks, and controls determined by the management to be vital to preventing the occurrence of a catastrophic release.

“Any piece of equipment or machinery that could significantly impair the ability to safely meet corporate business objectives, quality levels or environmental standards as identified in the business plan.” Equipment and other systems determined to be essential in preventing the occurrence of, or mitigating the consequences of an uncontrolled event. Such equipment may include vessels, machinery, piping, blowout preventers, wellheads and related valving, flares, alarms, interlocks, fire protection equipment, and other monitoring, control, and response systems. Equipment and other systems determined to be essential in preventing the occurrence of, or mitigating the consequences of an uncontrolled event.

5. CRITICAL EQUIPMENT IDENTIFICATION

A critical equipment identification approach for condition-based maintenance (CBM) planning in the beverage plant is presented. In this study, critical equipment in the beverage industry was identified for effective condition-based maintenance planning. The approach involves multiplying four generic factors, namely; the probability of failure, losses in in-process materials, mean-time-to-repair (MTTR) and mean cost of repairs. The score for the probability of failure was estimated as a function of cumulative failure rate (CFR) of the respective plant equipment. Four grades of equipment failure probability were used: very low probability of failure, low probability of failure, the medium probability of failure and high probability of failure. MTTR was determined from the identified probability distribution described by the repair data of the reference equipment. Losses in in-process materials were computed from a comparison of the total throughput and the lost brews. The results show that the Dust aspirator, weighing bin, Mash filter and Chain conveyors with average criticality index of 0.2712, 0.2199, 0.1350 and 0.1563 respectively, are the most critical equipment in a beverage plant. This implies that planning and control of maintenance on the identified critical equipment based on condition monitoring will help improve the production efficiency in the brewing process.

6. EXAMPLES OF CRITICAL EQUIPMENT

Highly Critical – Governmental Regulation – Waste Water Treatment Plant – Sludge Disposal System Highly Critical - Central System: – Chilled Water – Compressed Air Critical - Throughput Affected: – Cooling Towers – Electrical Substations Critical - High-Cost Impact: – Substation Transformers – Chillers suppliers can assist distilleries throughout each stage of the distilling process, from mating through to maturation. They should supply equipment for precise distillery installation demands, whether distilleries are looking to upgrade and expand their current distilling operations or start from scratch with a brand-new distillery. Following is the range of products known as critical equipment in the distillery industry.

- **Inoxpa:** An example of a manufacturer who can provide an entire solution for the distilling industry, especially for demanding hygienic processes, is Inoxpa. Their products include

butterfly valves, check valves, overflow valves, strainers and pumps. BME can supply a full range of its equipment for all your application needs.

- **Unitech:** The Unitech split bodied, solid PTFE seated butterfly valve was developed especially for the distilling industry. This valve can be used in both manual and automated distilleries.
- **Orbinox:** For the mashing process in the distilling sector, we have Orbinox EX and BC knife gate valves. The mashing process requires precise valves, to achieve the right end product.
- **Zwick:** To meet the demand for double block and bleed isolation on steam lines, BME supplies the Zwick tri-block valve due to its efficient performance and space-saving properties.
- **NTC:** NTC ball valve. This valve is used for critical applications within the distilling process, such as a still outlet, charging, discharging and vent valves.
- **ADCA:** Steam products within the distilling industry are sourced from ADCA. ADCA provides equipment for all your distilling requirements. For example, steam control valves, reducing valves, heat exchangers separators and steam traps, etc.

7. ELEMENTS OF MAINTENANCE SUCCESS IN THE CHEMICAL INDUSTRY

The chemical industry is comprised of many segments with diverse and complex operations, which can make a standardized maintenance approach challenging. Batch operation chemical plants typically have more frequent opportunities for preventive maintenance activities, which can provide greater flexibility for maintenance planning and labour scheduling than continuous operation facilities. Regardless of product segments or operational processes, comprehensive asset intelligence, effective preventive maintenance (PM), and efficient labour scheduling are three fundamental elements to ensure chemical industry maintenance success.

- **Comprehensive Asset Intelligence:** Knowing the history of the equipment, and having immediate access to that information, is a vital element of effective maintenance. Consider a polymer process, where if the reactor agitator goes down, the polymer can harden inside the reactor within an hour or so. When the polymer hardens, it can take between two and four days to have the reactor cleaned. In addition to the maintenance and cleaning costs, all this wasted time contributes to accumulating production losses. If the prior work order history is not easily accessible and readily available, it is unlikely that the maintenance technician will be able to review it in time to get the agitator repaired quickly. However, with a comprehensive CMMS like Accruent's Maintenance Connection, the entire work order history of the agitator can be viewed quickly by the technician to troubleshoot the issue and get the agitator back into service faster. With Maintenance Connection, the technician also has easy access to maintenance and operational documents, procedures, instructions and drawings that can assist in improving repair times.
- **Effective Preventive Maintenance:** In the past, maintenance work was typically reactive. Schedules, usually established manually, lacked consideration for the capacity and availability of resources. As a result, these schedules were followed loosely, if at all. Now, scheduling assesses the availability of skills and parts and includes analytics for optimization. From the maintenance management perspective, strong asset intelligence information provides an opportunity to identify trends and shift maintenance activities from reactive, unplanned downtime events to proactive preventive maintenance. For example, looking at the collective work order history of a particular motor, it may become evident that the motor fails after 5,000 hours of use. With this data, Maintenance Connection's Preventive Maintenance Software can be used to deliver scheduled PM work orders based on equipment usage. Why is this shift to the preventive maintenance approach important? One recent report indicates that manufacturing companies lose \$50 billion annually in unplanned downtime.² When an unplanned downtime event occurs in a chemical plant during off-hours, labour costs increase because of overtime, expedited materials and equipment needed for repairs, and production loss for significant periods of time. When equipment maintenance is planned, the parts can be available, the labour scheduling, and the maintenance performed in a more efficient manner. Production downtime can also be predicted, meaning operations can potentially build product inventory levels in a way that customer shipments are still made and production revenue losses do not occur.
- **Efficient Labour Scheduling:** One of the key challenges facing maintenance managers in the chemical industry has reduced staffing to maintain aging facilities. It is critical then that

labour is scheduled in a manner that maximizes efficiency and drives labour productivity. Leveraging the asset work history within Maintenance Connection can help managers improve the accuracy of estimated repair times to fix equipment. This accuracy can aid the labour planning process as well. Maintenance Connection's Planning and Scheduling ultimately help drive efficient labour scheduling by giving maintenance managers and schedulers: Granular visibility into staffing assignments, Flexible views to see assignments in different ways (e.g., calendar view), The ability to automate assignments, Generated PM work orders based on a variety of triggers.

- **Maintenance Success:** There are many factors that contribute to maintenance success, and the chemical industry's diversity of processes, facility sizes, etc. can make it challenging to establish effective maintenance programs across all assets. The cornerstone of maintenance success is a strong CMMS that can deliver three core benefits: comprehensive asset intelligence, effective preventive maintenance (PM), and efficient labour scheduling. Summary This paper presents a model to manage safety critical equipment and systems. It also discusses some practical ways to comply with the operations and maintenance aspect of the safety life cycle. Although the main focus of this discussion is Safety Instrumented Systems, the management model is applied broadly to manage equipment and systems that form the last line of defense against hazardous events, such as safety relief valves. The approach has been developed and tested over a considerable period of time and has been continuously improved as the standards and improved technologies have emerged. Ideas on developing management procedures, training, proof testing and performance analysis improve the reliability of safety-critical systems are discussed in some detail.
- **The Management Model:** The objective of this management model is to provide the needed focus on the integrity of safety critical equipment and systems. To remain competitive, organizations cannot afford to over maintain these systems. However, maximum safety must be ensured in order to minimise the risk of incidents. Therefore, management processes and strategies have to be:
 - Robust
 - Practical to use
 - Have leadership at the right level
 - Define clear responsibilities
- **Improve performance:** The proposed model to manage safety critical equipment, devices and systems are shown in figure 1. The key elements of this model are:
 - a) Having a clear corporate policy on management of safety-critical equipment, devices and systems
 - b) Defining the requirements and standards that reflect the policy
 - c) Having detailed procedures for proof testing and defeats
 - d) Training people on these procedures and equipment

Fig. 1 - Model for managing Safety Critical Equipment and Systems

- e) Scheduling and testing of safety-critical equipment and systems
- f) Having a system for recording test results
- g) Analysing performance
- h) Improvement programs to eliminate gaps and bad actors
- i) Assessing the model for its effectiveness at an operational as well as management levels:

Tahir Rafique, Douglas Lloyd, Ken Evans, A Practical Approach to Managing Safety Critical Equipment and Systems in Process Plants, Lead Electrical and Instruments Engineer: Qenos Botany Site, Session One: A Practical Approach to Managing Safety Critical Equipment and Systems in Process Plants.

8. CONCLUSION

Maintaining and prioritising vast quantities of equipment necessary for upstream operations are challenging. Managing the sheer volume of equipment and reporting data in order to satisfy numerous regulations can be an ongoing, uphill battle. But with Absoft's Critical Equipment Management service, you can ensure that your people, assets and environments are safe, and that you meet the most stringent global governance standards. You can easily prove your compliance without the usual difficulty and stress that's involved.

First, ask yourself: What process do we follow if a fire door doesn't close in 20 seconds? How do we decide which equipment is more critical? Do we have an up to date closed loop maintenance book at all times? Are we in total control of maintenance, with full visibility at all times? When we identify a problem, what do we do about it? Do we use a best practice method for improving maintenance processes? Are you using SAP Plant Maintenance to its full capacity? If you can't answer these types of questions, then you may not be operating at an adequate level when it comes to operational safety and compliance.

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